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Abstract

Deep in history, the influence of the Kipchak Turks on a wide geography stretching from the Central Asian steppes to India, through Anatolia, the Caucasus and the Middle East to North Africa, is a topic often discussed in academic circles and among history buffs. Within this wide area of influence, the traces of the Kipchaks on the Mamluk state are particularly striking. The Mamluks were founded under the leadership of leaders of Kipchak origin and survived their golden age thanks to the strategic intelligence of these leaders. Generals such as Baybars, Kalavun and Khalil expanded the borders of the state and increased its international reputation. The purpose of this article is to study the influence and historical legacy of such a Kipchak leader as Beybars on the Mamluk state. The focus will be on how Baybars, outstanding for his cultural and political contributions, as well as his military successes, shaped the course of history and what impact he had on world history. How Baybars' leadership abilities, managerial skills and strategic decisions influenced the peak periods of the Mamluk state.

Keywords: Anatolia, Baybars, Islamic history, Kipchaks, Mongols, Caliphate.

Introduction: The history of the Kipchag tribes is intertwined with the history of the life and formation of Sultan Beybars, a Turkic Kipchak who was born in 1233 in the north of the Black Sea. He was probably captured by the Mongols when he was fourteen years old. He was taken prisoner to Damascus via Sivas Aleppo and sold there in the slave market. The man who captured Baybars was Aytekin el-Bundukdari, one of the Mamluks of the Ayyubid Sultan Salih Eyyub. Later, in 1246, when his mind was noticed by Salih Eyyub, he was bought by him and sent to military barracks for military training. After completing his education, Baybars joined the army, took part in a number of conflicts with the Crusaders and in a short time received the title of emir. Baybars achieved his first major military success by defeating Louis IX of France, including several hundred Templars. He won the Battle of Mansour (1250), where, as commander of the Ayyubid army, he defeated the Crusader army of 1,500 men under the command of Louis (Amitai-Preiss, 1996). During the Seventh Crusade, Crusader forces landed troops in Damietta, but Fahreddin, the commander of the Mamluk military unit in the region, could not prevent the landing and retreated. When the residents of the city saw that the Mamluk soldiers were not defending the city, they panicked and left. The Crusader army occupied the city, and then moved towards Cairo. At night they set up camp on the banks of the Nile. The Mamluk army is also in its camp on the opposite shore. In the morning, Robert Artois, commander of the vanguard of the Crusader army, crossed the river, without waiting for most of the army to cross the river to make a surprise raid, and retreated three kilometers to Mansoura (Çalık, 2008). At dawn, he very quickly attacked the headquarters of the Ayyubid army from a distance. Egyptian soldiers were killed before they could take up their weapons, and a small number of them managed to escape to Mansour (Ergun, 2002). Robert decided to expand on this success and move to Mansour, and then quickly moved to Mansour to destroy all Egyptian troops. Baybars, who kept his cool, took command instead of Commander Fahreddin, who died in the raid,

gathered the fugitive soldiers, put them under his command and prepared to defend the city. Baybars personally stationed his soldiers in the center of the city and ordered them to hide, while he opened the main entrance to the city. When Robert's vanguard forces approached the city, Robert thought that the city had been evacuated, and quickly drove to the center of the city, to the inner walls of the castle. When Baybars gave the command to attack, the Crusader heavy cavalry, which could not fight in the narrow streets and squares, was destroyed. Very few managed to get out of the city on foot or on horseback. Among the dead was the brother of King Louis Robert of France, famous Knights Templar such as Guillaume de Sonnac (Smith, 1984). When most of the Crusader army arrived at Mansour, Baybars failed to repel them with successive offensives, which he launched between 8 and 11 February. He remained on the defensive and successfully and stubbornly defended the city until April 5, 1250. As a result, on this day, the Crusader army lifted the siege under the onslaught of the main forces of the Ayyubid army. They failed to retreat to the coast, and the entire Crusader army and many French nobles, including their commander, the French king, were captured. Muazzam Turanshah, the then Ayyubid Sultan of Egypt, did not appreciate the productive efforts of the Mamluk troops in the battle in question as much as they expected. Moreover, the Mamluks supported Turanshah in his ascension to the throne. Moreover, he deposes the Mamluk emirs who have served since his father's time and appoints them as his relatives. The Mamluk emirs were naturally very alarmed by this development. As a result, a group of Mamluk officers led by Baybars took action and killed Turanshah on April 30, 1250. Thus, the rule of the Ayyubid dynasty in Egypt ended with the death of Turanshah (Köse, 2010). The Mamluk emirs, who already held strong positions, now had the right to decide on public administration issues. However, they are all nervous about the Sultan's appointment. The accession to the throne of the Mamluk emir, and not a representative of the dynasty, would cause unrest among the

people. By the Sultan's decision, the Mamluk emirs, after some discussion, decided to elect Shecheruddur, the wife of Salih Eyyub, as sultan. The factors were undoubtedly the fact that she was the widow of a member of the dynasty, her understanding of state affairs and her close relationship to the Mamluks. However, it soon became clear that a woman would not be welcome in Muslim society. The reaction began to grow both among the population of the country and from the rulers of other Muslim countries. In particular, Abbasi Mustasim Billah's somewhat excessive letter to Baghdad made the situation unclear. In his letter, the caliph says: "If there is no one among you who could become sultan, I will send a man from Baghdad to you." After that, Shecheruddur married the Mamluk Emir Aybeg and left him the throne. Thus, the Mamluk became the head of state, and the Mamluk state was officially established.

The results of the study: Aybeg's marriage to Shecheruddur and her ascension to the Mamluk throne worried the Mamluks of Bahri. A group of Mamluks, firmly loyal to the family of Salih Ayyub, strongly preferred that Aybeg appoint Melik of the Ayyubids as head of state. As a result, a conflict arose between the Bahrim Mamluks and the Oghuz group within the Mamluks. Aybeg's formation of a group of Mamluks from slaves loyal to him and his punishment of the Bahri Mamluks who opposed him forced these Mamluks to flee Egypt to the Ayyubid rulers in Syria, to Kerak, Damascus and Palestine, and about 130 of them to the Anatolian Seljuks. After some time, Aybeg ordered Seifeddin Kutuz to kill the Mamluk emir Fariseddin Aktai, in whom he saw a threat to his position, thus putting a large group of Mamluks who supporters of Aktai in a much more difficult situation were. Beybars, who for some time was the emir of the Bahri Mamluks, at a meeting with them explained the need to fight Aybeg, but when the majority did not support him, he wrote to Nasir Yusuf, the Sultan of Syria of the Ayyubids: and offered to join his team with his people. When he was accepted, he went to Syria. Kutuz, who allegedly had a hand in the murder of Aybeg in the bath, dominated the throne and established a balance between the Oghuz and the Kipchak Mamluks. In Syria, Baybars incited Nasser Yusuf to attack Egypt, while he and his men plundered the regions under Egyptian rule. Aybeg asked the Abbasid Caliph for help, and when he failed to get help, he prepared an army and sent it to Syria. Nasir Yusuf and Baybars were defeated, and with the intervention of the Abbasid Caliph, a ceasefire was reached between the two sides. In this agreement, there was a condition for the transfer of the Bahrian Mamluks to Egypt, on the other hand, Baybars quarreled with Nasser Yusuf. Therefore, Baybars left Syria and came under the protection of the regent of Kerak (an area in Jordan). He marched against an Egyptian unit nearby with reinforcements received from here but was again defeated in the conflict. In Egypt, Aybeg Bahri continues his position against the Mamluks, and the emirs, very concerned about the situation, go to Kerak, to Baybars. On the other hand, they are putting pressure on Baybars to speak out against Aybeg. Bay-

bars marched on Egypt again with some reinforcements. Aybeg sent an army under the command of Kutuz, and this time Baybars was defeated and retreated. Kutuz killed Bahri's Mamluk prisoners without delay. When the regent of Kerak did not let Baybars and his companions into the city, they again took refuge with Nasir Yusuf. The person who saved the Bahrian Mamluks from the oppression of Aybeg was Shajar al-Dur, whom the Egyptian historian Ibn Taghriberdi presented as a "beautiful, pious and intelligent woman." Aybeg was killed by one of his subordinates while he was in the bathhouse in 1257. However, the Mamluks of Bahri, whom he always supported and saw support from them, now lost their former power, they failed to protect Shajar al-Dura, and he was killed after a while. Then the Mamluks loyal to Aybeg put his 15-year-old son on the throne and made Sultan regent of Kutuz because of his young age. Soon Kutuz imprisoned the young sultan and his mother, killed prominent Mamluk emirs of Bahri and ascended to the throne. The Mongols captured Baghdad in 1258, killed the Abbasid Caliph al-Mustasim and his family, and then spread further into Northern Syria. The Mongol invasion besieged and captured Aleppo in 1259. Then in 1260 they turned their offensive into Egypt. Nasser Yusuf's army dispersed when it received news of the Mongol offensive. Meanwhile, Baybars learned that Sultan Kutuz was preparing for war, and sent word that he wanted to be under his command. Realizing that it was impossible to hold on only for the Mamluks loyal to him against the Mongol expansion and that he had no other choice but to mobilize the Bahrian Mamluks, Kutuz accepted this offer from Baybars, who, as he knew, had strong power over them. After that, in March 1260, Baybars returned to Egypt, taking a promise from Kutuz to spare his life. Kutuz appointed Baybars commander of the vanguard of the Mamluk army and promised that he would capture Aleppo if the war was won. Hulagu Khan sent a message to the Mamluk Sultan Kutuz and asked Egypt to "become a province." Of course, this request was rejected. The second brilliant achievement of Baybars' military career was his role as commander of the vanguard of the Mamluk army at the Battle of Ain Jalut on September 3, 1260. When the army was ready, they went on a campaign. Arriving in Akka, they received news that the Mongol army was advancing south from the east of the Dead Sea (Fayed Hammâd Âşûr, 1976). In this regard, Kutuz sent an army to the southeast, to Ain Jalut, located south of the Dead Sea, to meet with the Mongol army. After a while, the Mongol army appeared and the battle began. It is claimed that the real war plan was prepared by Baybars, who knew the region well after leaving Egypt (Dühmân, 1990). According to this plan, while most of the army was hiding behind trees, Baybars and his own unit fought the Mongol army for several hours using attack-and-run tactics, and then diverted the Mongols to an area where most of the army was waiting in ambush. The Mamluks surrounded the Mongol army in a short time. As a result of the fierce battle, most of the Mongolian army, including the Mongolian commander Ketboga Noyan, was destroyed.

Some time after the battle, Baybars asked Kutuz to surrender Aleppo. Kutuz did not fulfill his promise and handed over Aleppo to a person close to him. There was already a feud between them that lasted for some time and deepened. After this latest incident, Baybars found Kutuz's attempts to break the influence of the Bahrian Mamluks unbearable and informed his close friends that he had decided to kill Kutuz (Gül, 2002). Meanwhile, after Kutuz restored order in Syria after the battle, the army moved to Egypt. When Kutuz went hunting to the place where the camp was set up for the night, Baybars found a long-awaited opportunity and on October 22, 1260, killed Kutuz along with several of his comrades (Çalık, 2008). When the state dignitaries gathered to determine the new sultan, they unanimously chose Baybars. When they entered the tent, they were greeted by atabeg and Sultan's regent Farisuddin Aktai. When he learned from them that Sultan Kutuz was dead, he asked: "Which one of you killed him?" and Baybars replied, "Me." To this answer, atabek said, "My khan, sit on his throne." As one can understand, it seemed natural that the man who killed Kutuz would become sultan. On the same day, October 26, 1260, he went to Kalata'l-Sebel and sat on the Mamluk throne. Kalata'l-Sebel is a castle and its palaces, the construction of which was started by Salahaddin Ayyubi in 1176 as the center of the sultanate. One of his first actions when he ascended the throne was to reduce the taxes levied by Kutuz. This decision mitigated public discontent caused by the fact that the man who killed the sultan ascended to the throne and aroused favor for Baybars. Meanwhile, internal uprisings were taking place. Some of them were led by Kutuz people or members of the Ayyubid dynasty. Baybars suppressed the uprisings and captured the rebellious emirs, but later forgave them and restored them to their former positions (Ibn Tağriberdi, 1972). After settling internal problems, Baybars needed to eliminate external threats to the security of the newly created Mamluk Sultanate. These threats were as follows: there were problems with the Armenian Cilician Kingdom in the north and with the crusader counties in the coastal Levant, which often collaborated with the Mongols. The Ilkhanate also sought to regain Ain Jalut. As a result of internal settlements, the Crusader kingdoms in the Levant, the Armenian Kingdom of Cilicia and the Ilkhanid Khanate in Cilicia became the main enemies of his country. Against these enemies, Baybars tried to form alliances with rulers with whom there was no conflict of interest. Speaking about the strength of the Mamluk state, it should be noted its links with many ruling dynasties and neighboring states in general. Here, it should be noted that Sultan Beybars' relations with the Anatolian Seljuks were important, which determined the course of history, especially with the deposed sultan of the Anatolian Seljuks Izzeddin Keykavus II. The correspondence between Keykavus and Baybars led to an alliance during the period when Keykavus retired to Antalya. This approach to the alliance did not end even when Keykavus fled to Constantinople, and even if it did not lead to any joint venture, he remained alive until Keykavus' death. In the early years of Beybars' rule, the khan of the Golden Horde state was Khan Berke, who

converted to Islam before becoming khan. Although there were disagreements between him and his uncle's son Hulagu Khan over Azerbaijan and even hostility due to Hulagu Khan's attacks on Islamic countries, for Baybars, this hostility between the two Mongolian khanates opened up opportunities that he could use for the benefit of his country. To this end, Baybars established friendly relations between the two countries through diplomatic channels. This friendship represented an alliance beneficial to both rulers. Baybars' first correspondence with Khan Berke took place in 1261, immediately after his accession to the throne, and it is assumed that Baybars' letter was dated November 1261. Berke Khan's reply was written on May 11, 1263, and this day is considered the date of the conclusion of the alliance between the Mamluk Sultanate and the Golden Horde state (Williams, 1984). It is claimed that Baybars was the first ruler in the history of Islam who sought systematic and permanent diplomatic contacts with the Christian world. The trade agreement he concluded with the Byzantine Emperor Michael VIII in 1261 was, in a sense, a search for an alliance. Then another trade agreement was concluded with Genoa. These agreements did not bring any obvious benefits to the other side but allowed Baybars to keep abreast of events and trends in Europe. On the other hand, he established contact with the Sicilian Hohenstaufen dynasty, which was seen as a serious obstacle to the papacy's eastern ambitions. However, when this dynasty broke up in 1266, she immediately got involved with others. It is claimed that these contacts were the most obvious reason that the Eighth Crusade headed to Tunisia in 1271. A year after his accession to the throne, Baybars began fighting against the Crusaders. When it became known that Bohemond had concluded an agreement with the Ilkhans, he took action and laid siege to Antakia. Despite the fact that he failed, he tried again the following year, but again did not achieve any results. He continued his attacks to completely expel the Crusaders from the Middle East, and in February 1265 captured Caesarea, Jaffa, Ascalon and Arsuf between Haifa and Jaffa. The following year, he moved to Acre. However, Safed was attacked when it turned out that it was too protected. Then Ramla was captured. In the same year, the second Mamluk army was sent under the command of Kalavun to punish Hetum I, the ruler of the Armenian Kingdom of Cilicia, who was allied with the Ilkhans. The army of Hetum I was defeated in August 1266, and Adana, Misis, Tarsus and Sis (Kozan) were plundered. During these two years, Cilicia has caused serious damage to the Armenian Kingdom. Baybars continued his attacks, changing directions one by one, and in 1267 attacked Tiberias and the vicinity of Akka. With all these military actions, Baybars isolated Antakia, the last Crusader castle. He decided that it was time to march on Antakia, and in early April 1268 he besieged the city. The city fell after a short siege. Sultan Baybars and his army besieged the city of Antakia in 1268, and on May 8 the city surrendered. Sultan Baybars destroyed the city castle, killed most of the Christians who participated in the defense of the city, and captured some of them. The fall of Antakia was a severe blow to the Christian world, and the

Crusader presence in the Levant began to weaken rapidly. A fleet with soldiers was sent to Cyprus, as the King of Cyprus tried to unite the Crusader forces in the Levant and attacked Muslim ships sailing in the Mediterranean Sea. However, the fleet was caught in a storm off the coast of Cyprus, and many ships sank. Thus, this naval expedition failed. Baybars was concerned that the loss of Antakia from the Crusaders might lead to a new crusade and that the Crusader army that came to the Levant with this expedition would march on Egypt. Therefore, he decided that it was necessary to further narrow the presence of the crusaders in the region, and in 1271 he entered the territory of the county of Tripoli. He took Hisnu-l-Ekrad, Hisnu-Akkar, Safita and the castle of the Teutonic Knights Hisnu-l-Karin, located northeast of Akka, and some other castles. Thus, the Crusaders' presence in the Middle East was limited to only a few towns on the coast.

The fight against the Ilkhanate Sultan Baybars' military campaigns covered the regions between 1261 and 1277. Baybars had to send an army to the region after the Ilkhanid army besieged Birejik Castle in 1265. When the Ilkhanid army received news of Baybars' approach, it lifted the siege and retreated. Abaka Khan, who ascended the throne as the successor of Hulagu Khan in the same year, concluded an agreement with the crusaders in 1269 and moved to the outskirts of Aleppo. Baybars sent an army to this region, and he himself moved towards Syria. While they were still on their way, the news came that the Ilkhanid army had been defeated. Abaka Khan arrived in Antep with Crusader troops in 1271. Baybars defeated both forces in Harran. The following year, Abaka Khan again besieged Birejik, and when it became known about the approach of the Mamluk army, the siege was lifted. Another Ilkhanid attack on Birejik occurred in 1272. Baybars, who received the news that the Mongol army was encircling the city, moved on the city and defeated the vanguard forces of the Mongols who had marched near the city. As soon as the besieging troops found out about this incident, they lifted the siege and retreated. Despite all the conflicts with the Mamluk Sultanate, Abaka Khan repeatedly made peace proposals to Baybars, which Baybars rejected each time. One of them was made in 1266 by a delegation that brought gifts. Baybars rejected the proposal, citing the massacres committed by the Mongols in Islamic countries. Abak Khan's next attempt was in 1268 or 1269, when he wrote a letter containing harsher expressions and asking Baybars to obey him. The insulting expression "You are a slave. You were sold in Sivas, how can you write against the rulers of the earth in such a situation?" Another proposal came in 1272 as a request to send a delegation through Pervan Muyneddin Suleiman. This is the case when Baybars sent arrows and armor with his messenger. It is claimed that this peace, or rather the ceasefire proposals, were caused by the fact that the Ilkhanid State was in conflict with the Golden Horde State throughout this period. The Anatolian Expedition Sultan Baybars' decision to attack the Ilkhanate in Anatolia came immediately after Izzeddin Keykavus left the throne and took refuge in Antalya. In the autumn of

1261, Sultan Baybars sent an embassy delegation, inviting the deposed sultan to Egypt and promising him all possible assistance. Izzeddin Keykavus stated that if he returned to the throne of the Anatolian Seljuks with the help of Sultan Baybars, he would give Diyarbakir and its surroundings to the Mamluks. In addition, icta's decrees, signed by himself, were sent with empty fields for the name. Ibn Abduzahir, a well-known historian of the Bahri Mamluk period, claims that Izzeddin Keykavus promised half of the country's territory and sent a map demonstrating this. He claims that Diyarbakir was handed over to Ambassador Izzeddin Keykavus from Baybars. Upon learning about this, Sultan Baybars immediately began to prepare an army. However, an official in Konya and in the Ilkhanid palace discovered this correspondence and took the necessary countermeasures, sending a strong army to Anatolia. In this case, Izzeddin Keykavus and Sultan Baybars had to act very quickly, but the Mamluk army could not complete preparations for the campaign so quickly. In this situation, Izzeddin Keykavus took refuge in Byzantium. Nevertheless, these events marked the beginning of a new and extremely important era in the relations between the Anatolian Seljuks and the Mamluks. When Izzeddin Keykavus took refuge in Byzantium, the relations between the Anatolian Seljuks and the Mamluks were interrupted. A long time later, in 1272, at the initiative of the Anatolian Seljuk vizier Pervane Muyneddin Suleiman and the Ilkhanid governor in Anatolia, Samagar Noyan, a letter was sent to Sultan Beybars with a request to begin peace negotiations with the Ilkhanate. Sultan Baybars seems to have accepted this offer and sent a delegation to the Ilkhanid palace. The delegation first stopped in Anatolia, then went to the Ilkhanid palace together with Pervane Muyneddin Suleiman and handed a letter from Sultan Baybars to Abak Khan. The Sultan declared that the Mongols would remain friends only if they left the occupied lands. Abaka Khan, enraged, sent the Mamluk ambassadors back. It is noteworthy that Sultan Baybars sent Samagar-Noyan an arrow, and Abaka Khan an armor, which is interpreted by researchers as Baybars' desire to dominate Anatolia and a test for Abaka Khan. On the other hand, when Izzeddin Keykavus was in Antalya, he granted Sultan Baybars significant territories. Baybars claimed that he had rights to at least part of the Anatolian lands. Among the Anatolian Seljuks, the first Muyneddin Suleiman, with the approval of the Mongols, ordered the poisoning of Rukneddin Kilich Arslan in 1265 and enthroned the young Giyaseddin Keykhusrev III, who was less than six years old. Despite the sultan's young age, he ruled the Anatolian Seljuk state more or less independently, guided by the instructions of the Ilkhanid palace. However, the appointment of Akai Noyan and Samagar Noyan to Anatolia by the Ilkhanid ruler Abak Khan limited the freedom of movement of Pervane Muyneddin Suleiman. At first, he ruled the Noyans by bribery, but with increasing demands for bribes, his position became difficult, and in 1272 he complained to Abaka Khan about Akai Noyan, claiming that he was secretly meeting with the Mamluk sultan. When Abaka Khan stated that he would investigate and think about the situation, Pervane felt that his lies could be revealed

and that this would endanger his position, so in 1272-1273 he sent letters to Sultan Baybars asking him to come to Anatolia with an army and defeat the Mongols. On March 2, 1277, Sultan Baybars, at the head of the mighty Mamluk army, set off from Cairo to Anatolia. Passing through Aleppo, he left part of his forces here to prevent a possible flanking offensive by the Mongol army. On April 7, leaving Aleppo, a reconnaissance detachment sent by him captured and destroyed a Mongolian detachment of three thousand people. On April 13, the Mamluk army crossed the Ceyhan River and reached the Elbistan plain. The next day, April 14, the vanguard forces of the Ilkhanid army and the Anatolian Seljuks, having learned about the advance of Baybars, landed on the plain. The Anatolian army also included Armenian and Georgian troops subordinate to the state. The Ilkhanid army under the command of Tatabun Noyan and Tokun Noyan numbered 15-17 thousand people. The Anatolian Seljuk army was commanded by Pervane Muyneddin Suleiman. The Battle of Elbistan, which took place on April 15, ended with a heavy defeat of the Ilkhanid-Anatolian armies. After the defeat of Pervane, Muyneddin Suleiman managed to escape. During the battle, Pervane's son, grandson, brother-in-law, governors of Erzincan, Sivas, Sinop, an officer of Sivas and other high-ranking officials of the Anatolian Seljuk state were among those who defected to the Mamluks or surrendered. Some sources claim that the Anatolian Seljuk army did not engage in battle at all. Heavy losses of the Mongols are also reported, including the death of Tatabun Noyan. At the end of the campaign, Baybars stopped at the battlefield and asked the local scientists of Elbistan how many Mongolian corpses they counted. One of them claimed to have counted 6,770 corpses, not counting those Mongolian soldiers who were able to escape from the battlefield. Ibn Bibi, describing the battle of Elbistan, wrote that the Mongol warriors behaved like angry tigers, while the Mamluks were like leaves moving in the autumn wind. Despite the numerical After the battle, the Mamluk army marched to Kayseri, where it was joyfully welcomed by local dignitaries on April 22. Baybars took his place on the Anatolian throne, and his name was mentioned in Friday prayers instead of the name of the Seljuk sultan. Pervane Muyneddin Suleiman, who survived the battle, was appointed to a position in the II regiment, and Giyaseddin Keykhusrev took refuge in his castle with his family and 400 concubines. Sultan Baybars planned to return to Egypt, but received messages from Pervane Muyneddin Suleiman and Giyaseddin Keykhusrev asking them to stay in Anatolia. He decided to leave on April 25, despite calls to stay. Sultan Baybars, "...Since the invasion of the Tatars, they have been sinister (bad) people... From now on, there will be no cooperation or talks on this issue... We did not shed the blood of the Anatolian people and did not plunder their property... We did not have the dishonor to touch your property, which you wanted to give to the Tatars..." He gave the answer Some Anatolian Seljuk officials and scholars expressed a desire to accompany Sultan Baybars to Egypt with their families. Important and wealthy emirs, as well as members of Pervane Muyneddin Suleiman's family, including his son,

grandson and mother, were taken with them, some against their will. There were also several Mongols among those who wanted to follow Baybars. It is believed that Sultan Baybars pursued more significant strategic goals in the Anatolian campaign than simply saving the Anatolian Seljuks from Mongol domination. Due to the Mongol invasion of Anatolia, Egypt's commercial ties with the Kipchak region were interrupted, which disrupted the regular influx of slaves needed to upgrade the Mamluk army. Baybars sent a representative delegation to the Golden Horde state to resume this trade, but this delegation was accompanied by the Byzantine Emperor Michael VIII, who sought to avoid deterioration of relations with the Ilkhanids. The Byzantine Emperor arrested the members of the delegation. Baybars sought to expel the Mongols from Anatolia and restore land transport routes. Baybars returned to Damascus on June 10, 1277. After his return, he fell ill and died fourteen days later, on June 20, 1277.

Conclusion: One of the first problems faced by Baybars after his accession to the throne was the legitimacy of the Mamluk state. For Islamic states, legitimacy meant recognition by the Caliph. However, since the Mamluk Sultanate was a slave-owning state, it was difficult to obtain such a title. After the accession of the Shecheruddur woman to the throne, relations with the Caliphate deteriorated. The caliphate was abolished as a result of the Ilkhanid attack, but Baybars was able to prevent the destruction of Baghdad by the Ilkhanids and invited Hakim I (Ebul-Qasim Ahmed), a member of the Abbasid dynasty, who was declared caliph in June 1261, to Cairo. Baybars provided the new caliph with the necessary legitimacy by handing over to him the administration of all Islamic lands. The name of the Caliph began to be read in sermons and written on coins. Baybars was an extremely successful ruler, his period of administration is considered the beginning of a new era in the history of the Mamluks. He has significantly strengthened stability in the region, ensuring unity and protection against external threats. After his death, he left behind a legacy as one of the most important rulers in the history of the Mamluks, for which his name is respected in the Islamic world, especially in Egypt and Syria. The history of the Mamluk dynasty is vivid evidence of how the cultural and military influences of the Kipchaks left an indelible mark on the madrasah of the history of the Middle East. The Mamluks, who emerged from the ashes of slavery and conquest, were able not only to escape to power, but also to establish themselves as one of the most effective and durable ruling elites in the history of the Islamic world. Sultan Baybars, a Kipchak by birth, became one of the most prominent rulers of this dynasty. His military campaigns against the Crusaders and Mongols not only protected his state from external threats, but also provided the Mamluk Sultanate with a strategic advantage in the region. Moreover, his efforts to restore the caliphate in the person of Hakim I underline his desire for religious legitimacy and the strengthening of the Islamic identity of his rule. The Sultanate of Baybars left behind a legacy that transformed the political landscape of the Middle East, strengthened economic and cultural ties between different regions and laid the foundations for the

further flourishing of Islamic civilization. The Mamluk dynasty thus demonstrates how willpower and the desire for independence can lead to the creation of a powerful state, whose influence is still felt in history. The history of the Mamluks is not just a story about power and war; it is a story about how identity and cultural heritage can shape the destinies of peoples and civilizations, leaving lessons for future generations about the importance of resilience, leadership and wisdom.

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